

Revisiting the Performance of Deep Learning-Based Vulnerability Detection on Realistic Datasets: Appendix

May 2023

A.1 Description of the *Real-Vul* projects.

A brief description of the projects, along with project size and number of vulnerable and uncertain methods, are presented in Table 1

Table 1

Project	Description	Project Size (# of Functions)	# Vulnerable Functions	# Un- certain functions
Chromium	Open source browser	153,057	3,137	149,920
FFmpeg	Video and audio processing	7,071	85	6,986
ImageMagic	Image manipulation tool	1,401	201	1,200
Jasper	Image encoding tool	315	86	229
Krb5	Computer network authentication protocol	3151	106	3045
Linux	Operating system	91,392	1,477	89,915
Openssl	Encryption tool suit	2,568	110	2,458
Php-src	Interpreter for php-scripting language	3,613	104	3,509
Qemu	System emulator	7,739	82	7,657
Tcpdump	Computer network analyzing tool	612	140	472

A.2 Types of vulnerability in *Real-Vul* projects.

Types of vulnerability in each of the projects and their frequency are presented in the following Tables.

Table 2: CWE IDs available in Chromium.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-20	87761
CWE-119	67277
CWE-399	47694
CWE-787	25237
CWE-254	20596
CWE-200	20267
CWE-416	14070
CWE-732	13937
CWE-264	12553
CWE-362	10910
CWE-189	8291
CWE-284	4193
CWE-125	3193
CWE-79	1695
CWE-311	1430
CWE-287	1083
CWE-285	868
CWE-19	622
CWE-22	605
CWE-190	601
CWE-310	394
CWE-17	323
CWE-281	300
CWE-269	260
CWE-704	235
CWE-476	206
CWE-94	110
CWE-77	72
CWE-601	72
CWE-1021	63
CWE-668	26
CWE-862	21
CWE-664	17

Table 3: CWE IDs available in FFmpeg.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-119	1685
CWE-189	219
CWE-369	173
CWE-787	151
CWE-476	120
CWE-125	99
CWE-617	92
CWE-20	51
CWE-834	47
CWE-399	6
CWE-416	6
CWE-665	6
CWE-200	2

Table 4: CWE IDs available in Imagemagick.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-119	4967
CWE-125	437
CWE-20	283
CWE-189	263
CWE-399	233
CWE-772	218
CWE-476	103
CWE-617	63
CWE-22	59
CWE-754	50
CWE-787	50
CWE-284	37
CWE-415	33
CWE-369	29
CWE-416	28
CWE-834	22
CWE-190	10
CWE-835	4
CWE-19	2

Table 5: CWE IDs available in Jasper.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-190	16332
CWE-476	504
CWE-119	122
CWE-125	59
CWE-415	19
CWE-416	7
CWE-20	6

Table 6: CWE IDs available in Krb5.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-119	60358
CWE-617	32732
CWE-18	1204
CWE-415	137
CWE-476	133
CWE-287	54
CWE-264	36
CWE-200	30
CWE-90	19
CWE-255	16
CWE-20	12
CWE-189	6
CWE-284	3

Table 7: CWE IDs available in Linux.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-399	89353
CWE-404	43047
CWE-20	31110
CWE-362	23947
CWE-264	15242
CWE-189	9253
CWE-416	7776
CWE-119	7725
CWE-200	3408
CWE-476	3285
CWE-310	3120
CWE-400	2199
CWE-17	2098
CWE-19	1871
CWE-285	1652
CWE-190	1129
CWE-787	944
CWE-388	752
CWE-125	587
CWE-284	514
CWE-287	426
CWE-415	188
CWE-732	174
CWE-772	146
CWE-59	122
CWE-254	86
CWE-617	82
CWE-704	66
CWE-16	58
CWE-191	48
CWE-120	26
CWE-665	24
CWE-755	23
CWE-835	16
CWE-358	16
CWE-754	15
CWE-862	14
CWE-532	11
CWE-763	9
CWE-129	7
CWE-369	6

Table 8: CWE IDs available in Openssl.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-310	497
CWE-20	448
CWE-190	434
CWE-399	409
CWE-330	231
CWE-119	187
CWE-125	158
CWE-200	144
CWE-254	66
CWE-189	56
CWE-362	28
CWE-320	20
CWE-400	18
CWE-476	17
CWE-17	12
CWE-787	5

Table 9: CWE IDs available in Php-src.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-190	1479
CWE-125	550
CWE-415	506
CWE-119	307
CWE-189	211
CWE-476	183
CWE-20	109
CWE-400	92
CWE-134	46
CWE-416	43
CWE-79	41
CWE-74	20
CWE-918	18
CWE-502	17
CWE-787	7
CWE-264	4

Table 10: CWE IDs available in Qemu.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-125	639
CWE-119	466
CWE-399	380
CWE-20	251
CWE-835	244
CWE-190	89
CWE-200	71
CWE-787	68
CWE-400	62
CWE-617	46
CWE-732	39
CWE-189	28
CWE-264	18
CWE-772	12
CWE-369	3

Table 11: CWE IDs available in Tcpdump.

CWE ID	Count
CWE-125	1641
CWE-835	51
CWE-119	42
CWE-120	32
CWE-674	20
CWE-20	8

Table 12: Project wise train dataset split date

Project Name	Train Split (GMT Time)		
	# commits	Start Date	End Date
Chrome	2,509	August 03, 2006	April 06, 2018
FFmpeg	68	August 03, 2013	May 30, 2018
ImageMagick	160	January 06, 2015	January 10, 2017
jasper	68	September 19, 2016	November 12, 2016
krb5	84	May 29, 2012	January 27, 2016
linux	1,181	October 16, 2006	May 10, 2017
openssl	88	June 01, 2000	August 24, 2016
php-src	83	May 20, 2013	October 24, 2016
qemu	65	September 20, 2011	October 17, 2016
tcpdump	112	October 22, 2014	September 13, 2017

Table 13: Project wise test dataset split date

Project Name	Test Split (GMT Time)		
	# commits	Start Date	End Date
Chrome	628	April 06, 2018	November 26, 2019
FFmpeg	17	June 28, 2018	August 05, 2019
ImageMagick	41	July 18, 2017	August 18, 2019
jasper	18	November 12, 2016	March 04, 2017
krb5	22	January 27, 2016	December 08, 2018
linux	296	May 10, 2017	July 17, 2019
openssl	22	September 10, 2019	September 01, 2020
php-src	21	October 30, 2016	January 19, 2019
qemu	17	October 17, 2016	August 20, 2019
tcpdump	28	September 13, 2017	September 13, 2018

A.3 Dataset split dates.

The dataset split dates for each of the projects are presented in Table 12 and 13.

A.4 Data Augmentation

Data augmentation is a strategy used in machine learning and artificial intelligence to enhance the volume and diversity of training data. By applying various transformations or introducing variability to existing data samples, data augmentation helps models generalize better to unseen data, thus improving their accuracy and robustness. This is particularly useful when the available dataset is limited or lacks diversity, which is a common challenge in many machine-learning tasks. In natural language processing (NLP), data augmentation might involve techniques such as synonym replacement, sentence shuffling, or back-translation, where sentences are translated to a different language and then back to the original language to introduce paraphrasing. These methods help in creating a more comprehensive linguistic dataset, enabling NLP models to capture a wider range of language nuances and contexts.

Dead code is defined as segments within a codebase that either are not executed at all or, if executed, do not influence the output. To enhance our existing code snippets, we incorporated such dead code. We developed 11 different augmentation methods in total. These methods are grounded in two core principles: firstly, the augmentation should not alter the code’s ability to compile, and secondly, it should not affect the output produced by the code snippet. We have applied 11 distinct techniques for augmentation. Our approach involves using tree-sitter¹ to analyze the source code, allowing us to pinpoint the variables within methods and their respective types. Following this analysis, we proceed to augment these methods or variables, or alternatively, we introduce code at various points between existing lines. A detailed explanation of these techniques is provided below.

1. **Digit assignment:** In this technique, a random digit will be assigned to a random variable of type ‘int,’ ‘long int,’ ‘double,’ and ‘float.’ In Code 1, we present a simple C++ code to generate a Fibonacci number, and in Code 2, we present the same code augmented by the digit assignment augmentation technique. The highlighted line in Code 2 represents the line that has been added.

Code 1: Original C++ code

```
1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         }
5         else {
6             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
7         }
8     }
9     int main() {
10        int n;
```

¹<https://github.com/tree-sitter/tree-sitter>

```

11     std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12     std::cin >> n;
13     std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14     return 0;
15 }

```

Code 2: Digit assignment augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             long int variable_5892652448478846722 =
↪ 1109593259642174996;
4             return n;
5         } else {
6             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
7         }
8     }
9     int main() {
10        int n;
11        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12        std::cin >> n;
13        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14        return 0;
15    }

```

2. **String assignment:** In this technique, a random string will be assigned to a random string variable. The technique has been presented in Code 3 using the code snippet presented in Code 1.

Code 3: String assignment augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7     }
8     int main() {
9         int n;
10        std::string variable_7939923253626245270 = "xSZemwZ";
11        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12        std::cin >> n;
13        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;

```

```

14     return 0;
15 }

```

3. **Digit addition:** In this technique, we randomly add two digits (any type of int,' long int,' double,' and 'float'). The addition can be done using *constant + constant* or *constant + variable* or *variable + constant*. The technique has been presented in Code 4

Code 4: Digit addition augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7     }
8     float variable_992644372901388726 = 4137453055618236745;
9     float variable_5809842273553661277 = 5617238862129559125
↪ + variable_992644372901388726;
10    int main() {
11        int n;
12        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
13        std::cin >> n;
14        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
15        return 0;
16    }

```

4. **Digit subtraction:** In this technique, we randomly subtract two digits (any type of int,' long int,' double,' and 'float'). The addition can be done using *constant - constant* or *constant - variable* or *variable - constant*. The technique has been presented in Code 5.

Code 5: Digit subtraction augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7     }
8     int main() {
9         int n;
10        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
11        int variable_7584887399247280005 =
↪ -6829392478367892955 - (648905433028734942);

```

```

12     std::cin >> n;
13     std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↳ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14     return 0;
15 }

```

5. **Digit multiplication:** In this technique, we randomly multiply two digits (any type of int, 'long int,' 'double,' and 'float'). The addition can be done using *constant * constant* or *constant * variable* or *variable * constant*. The technique has been presented in Code 6.

Code 6: Digit multiplication augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7     }
8     int main() {
9         int n;
10        double variable_918661341382313354 = -90572 * (73);
11        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12        std::cin >> n;
13        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↳ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14        return 0;
15    }

```

6. **Digit divide:** In this technique, we randomly divide two digits (any type of int, 'long int,' 'double,' and 'float'). The addition can be done using *constant/constant* or *constant/variable* or *variable/constant*. In this technique we make it confirm that no zero division error will occur if the code is compiled. The technique has been presented in Code 7.

Code 7: Digit division augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7         float variable_5300570152481195000 =
↳ -2014748430107523539;
8         float variable_2855398123176946640 =
↳ variable_5300570152481195000 / (6758817822866301597);

```

```

9     }
10    int main() {
11        int n;
12        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
13        std::cin >> n;
14        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
15        return 0;
16    }

```

7. **Additive identity:** In this technique, we add '0' to a randomly selected digit type (any type of int, 'long int,' 'double,' and 'float') variable introduced by the original code snippet. The technique has been presented in Code 8.

Code 8: Additive identity augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;
4         } else {
5             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
6         }
7     }
8     int main() {
9         int n;
10        n = n + 0;
11        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12        std::cin >> n;
13        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14        return 0;
15    }

```

8. **Multiplicative identity:** In this technique, we multiply '1' to a randomly selected digit type (any type of int, 'long int,' 'double,' and 'float') variable introduced by the original code snippet. The technique has been presented in Code 9.

Code 9: Multiplicative identity augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         n = n * 1;
3         if (n <= 1) {
4             return n;
5         } else {
6             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
7         }

```

```

8     }
9     int main() {
10        int n;
11        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12        std::cin >> n;
13        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
14        return 0;
15    }

```

9. **Conditional assignment:** In this technique, we use a condition statement ('if') to assign a constant in a variable. The condition can be always true or always false select that randomly. The technique has been presented in Code 10.

Code 10: Conditional assignment augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             float variable_40278342226607585 =
↪ 2120173673019239028;
4             if (variable_40278342226607585 < 0) {
5                 variable_40278342226607585 = -4710018000173632200;
6             }
7             return n;
8         } else {
9             return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
10        }
11    }
12    int main() {
13        int n;
14        std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
15        std::cin >> n;
16        std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
17        return 0;
18    }

```

10. **Loop:** In this technique, we use a loop statement ('for,' 'while') to augment the code snippet. The type of loop is selected randomly. The technique has been presented in Code 11.

Code 11: Loop augmentation

```

1     int fibonacci(int n) {
2         if (n <= 1) {
3             return n;

```

```

4      long int variable_8408319141485344038 =
↪ 8228008117673406334;
5      for (long int variable_241575333694102341 =
↪ -4591209994556770795; variable_241575333694102341 > 0;
↪ variable_241575333694102341--) {
6          variable_8408319141485344038--;
7      }
8      } else {
9          return fibonacci(n - 1) + fibonacci(n - 2);
10     }
11 }
12 int main() {
13     int n;
14     std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
15     std::cin >> n;
16     std::cout << "The " << n << "-th Fibonacci number is:
↪ " << fibonacci(n) << std::endl;
17     return 0;
18 }

```

11. **Code normalization:** In this technique, we normalize the input code segment. In code normalization, we rename all variables and methods to generic names (e.g., variable_1, function_3). The technique has been presented in Code 12.

Code 12: Code normalization

```

1      int function_1(int variable_1) {
2          if (variable_1 <= 1) {
3              return variable_1;
4          } else {
5              return function_1(variable_1 - 1) +
↪ function_1(variable_1 - 2);
6          }
7      }
8
9      int function_2() {
10         int variable_1;
11         std::cout << "Enter the value of n: ";
12         std::cin >> variable_1;
13
14         std::cout << "The " << variable_1 << "-th Fibonacci
↪ number is: " << function_1(variable_1) << std::endl;
15
16         return 0;
17     }

```

One of the major advantages of our augmentation strategy is that they can be chained/stacked together to form a complex augmentation strategy.

```

1 char * get_next_file(FILE * VFile, char * ptr) {
2     char * ret;
3     ret = fgets(ptr, PATH_MAX, VFile);
4     if (!ret)
5         return NULL;
6     if (ptr[strlen(ptr) - 1] == '\n')
7         ptr[strlen(ptr) - 1] = '\0';
8     return ret;
9 }

```

(a) Vulnerable method

```

1 #ifndef FPM_STR_H
2 #define FPM_STR_H 1
3
4 static inline char * str_purify_filename(char * dst, char * src, size_t size) /*
5- {{{ */ {
6     char * d, * end;
7     d = dst;
8     end = dst + size - 1;
9     for (; d < end && * src; ++d, ++src) {
10-        if (*(unsigned char*) src < ' ' || *(unsigned char*) src > '\x7f') {
11            *d = '.';
12-        } else {
13            *d = *src;
14        }
15    }
16    *d = '\0';
17    return d;
18 }
19 /* }}} */

```

(b) Uncertain (previously referred to as non-vulnerable) method.

Figure 1: Example of LIME explanation

A.5 Use of LIME for explanation

LIME [1], an explainability tool, to pinpoint the features influencing the models’ decisions. The choice of LIME over other similar tools like SHAP is due to its simpler and more interpretable insights for individual predictions, especially in complex models. LIME adopts a focused approach, centering its analysis around specific predictions and employing transparent models such as linear models or decision trees to elucidate the impact of individual features on the prediction outcome. In contrast, SHAP offers a broader, feature-based global explanation, which can be more intricate and resource-intensive. Our investigation with LIME uncovered the model’s reliance on particular tokens for its predictions. For example, we noticed a true positive case in Figure 1a and a false positive case in Figure 1b, both sharing a high similarity (cosine similarity of 0.97) according to the LIME model. In Figure 1a, the identified vulnerable method lacked a check for the ”strlen()” return value, potentially leading to out-of-bounds errors. Conversely, the method in Figure 1b, though uncertain (non-vulnerable), was labeled as vulnerable by the model due to the presence of tokens such as ”file” (lines 1 and 3 in Figure 1a and line 4 in Figure 1b) and ”0” (line 7 in Figure 1a and line 16 in Figure 1b), as indicated by LIME’s output.

References

- [1] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, and C. Guestrin, ““why should I trust you?”: Explaining the predictions of any classifier,” in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, San Francisco, CA, USA, August 13-17, 2016*, 2016, pp. 1135–1144.